

Furfuryl alcohol confirmed as key intermediate for furfurylthiol in coffee

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Abstract

Furfurylthiol (FFT) is a key odorant and largely determines the aroma of fresh roasted coffee. Earlier studies showed formation of FFT from furfuryl alcohol (FFA) and glutathione in aqueous model reactions. It was suggested that FFA and coffee proteins are precursors for sulphur odorants in coffee. The present study investigated the role of FFA in the formation of FFT during coffee roasting by “in-bean” experiments. Green coffee beans were soaked with FFA and freeze-dried. After roasting FFT was quantified by stable isotope dilution analysis. Spiking with FFA increased the FFT level in roasted coffee. In another experiment beans were spiked with deuterium labelled d_2 -FFA. After roasting the isotopologue distribution of FFT was determined. Beans spiked with labelled d_2 -FFA generated labelled d_2 -FFT and unlabelled furfural. These results unambiguously confirmed FFA as key intermediate for FFT in coffee. On the other hand, furfural, which does not originate from FFA, seems not related to FFT formation. The suggested formation pathway comprises formation of furfuryl cation from FFA, which reacts with protein-bound cysteine, and subsequent elimination of FFT from the protein-bound S-furfurylcysteine.

Keywords: coffee, aroma precursor, furfuryl alcohol, furfurylthiol, in-bean approach, stable isotope dilution analysis

Introduction

Coffee, after water and tea, is the third most popular beverage worldwide. It has little nutritional value and is mainly consumed for its stimulating character and delicious flavour. The aroma of brewed coffee is caused by around 22 key odorants [1]. The most important aroma compound is 2-furfurylthiol (FFT), which has a concentration of 1.1 mg/kg in roasted coffee and 19 μ g/L in a coffee brew; this exceeds 1900-times its odour threshold [1].

The formation pathway to FFT in coffee is still unclear. Various studies have tested potential precursors in model reactions. Aqueous reactions at 200 °C for 1 min between cysteine and various sugars as well as furfuryl alcohol (FFA) and furfural revealed furfural as the most potent precursor, followed by arabinose and FFA [2]. Consequently, the authors suggested furfural as an immediate precursor of FFT. Other experiments reacted solutions of FFA with various sulphur precursors such as cysteine, N-acetylcysteine and glutathione under reflux [3]. While cysteine was virtually ineffective, glutathione proved to be efficient as sulphur precursor. The author suggests protein-bound cysteine and FFA as precursors of FFT. The level of FFA generated during coffee roasting reaches up to 500 mg/kg [4]. This amount of FFA makes FFT a good precursor candidate to be investigated. However, it is still unclear how FFA will react under roasting conditions.

Roasting experiments with water-extracted green coffee beans surprisingly produced 60% more FFT than regular coffee beans [5] suggesting that FFT precursors in coffee are water-insoluble. Therefore, green coffee constituents like free cysteine, sucrose and other free sugars seem unlikely FFT precursors.

The “in-bean” approach, which was first proposed in 2001 [6] allowed to study coffee precursors under real roasting conditions. Green beans were spiked with potential precursors prior to roasting. Analyses of the roasted beans revealed higher formation of ethylated pyrazines after spiking with alanine [5]. In contrast, FFT formation was not favoured after spiking with arabinose. Furthermore, spiking with 13 C-labelled arabinose did not produce 13 C-labelled FFT. These findings support the hypothesis that FFT precursors are not water-soluble.

The present study investigated the role of FFA as potential intermediate of FFT during coffee roasting using the in-bean approach. Green beans were spiked with FFA, and the resulting FFT was measured in the roasted beans. After spiking with deuterium labelled d_2 -FFA the resulting FFT mass spectrum and isotopologue distribution in the roasted coffee was investigated.

Experimental

Materials

Green coffee (washed Arabica) was from Yunnan (China). The chemicals L-cysteine, LiAlD₄ and diethyl ether were from TCI (Tokyo, Japan). FFA was from Firmenich and d_2 -FFT from Aromalab (Planegg, Germany). Deuterium labelled d_2 -FFA was synthesised according to a slightly modified procedure of Sen and Grosch [8].

Spiking of coffee with precursors

Green coffee beans (50 g) were mixed with aqueous precursor solutions (20 g) and soaked at 50 °C during 4 h using a rotary evaporator. Then water (8 g) was added, and soaking was continued for another hour at 50 °C. The soaked beans were freeze-dried. Precursor solutions contained:

- FFA (50 mg)
- FFA (100 mg)
- FFA (150 mg)
- L-Cysteine (150 mg)
- L-Cysteine (150 mg) + FFA (50 mg)
- d₂-FFA (50 mg)
- d₂-FFA (100 mg)
- d₂-FFA (100 mg)

Coffee preparation

Dried coffee beans were roasted at small scale (17 g) in an IKAWA coffee roaster (Ikawa Ltd., London, England) at a temperature profile from 150 °C to 200 °C during 5 min. The roasted beans were immediately ground in an electric burr grinder (Baratza Encore, Bellevue, Washington, USA) at espresso grade. Freshly ground coffee powder (7 g) was used to produce approximately 35 ml espresso with a DeLonghi EC 680 espresso machine (Treviso, Italy). Coffee brews were immediately cooled in an ice bath prior to analysis.

Coffee analysis

Espresso brews (4 ml) were immediately analysed by solid-phase microextraction coupled to gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (SPME-GC-MS) in a 20 ml headspace vial. After conditioning at 40 °C for 10 min (250 rpm agitation), the headspace of the brew was extracted by a 75 µm DVB/CAR/PDMS fibre (2 cm length) at 40 °C for 30 min. Desorption was at 250 °C for 1 min in the GC injection port (splitless mode). GC analysis was on a DB-WAX column (30 m × 0.25 mm, i.d. 0.25 µm) with helium as carrier gas. The temperature was 45 °C isotherm for 5 min, then increased at 5 °C/min to 150 °C, followed by heating at 10 °C/min to 250 °C. Mass spectrometry was in EI mode (m/z 29-300).

Quantifications were by stable isotope dilution analysis [7]. For FFA quantification, samples were diluted 12.5-times with water prior to addition of the internal standard d₂-FFA. Ions m/z 81 and m/z 83 were used for quantification. For FFT quantification, cysteine (200 mg) was added in order to avoid oxidation and binding to the coffee matrix. Then the internal standard d₂-FFT was added. The ions m/z 114 and m/z 116 were used for quantification. Analyses were done in duplicate. Results are expressed as quantity of FFT per gram of green beans.

For the isotopologue study, green beans were spiked with deuterium labelled d₂-FFA. No standards were added prior to analysis.

Results and discussion

Spiking green coffee with FFA and/or cysteine

Coffee beans were spiked with either FFA (1-3 mg/g), cysteine (3 mg/g) or both FFA and cysteine (1+3 mg/g). The resulting concentrations of FFT are illustrated in Figure 1. FFT concentrations were determined in espresso brews and are expressed per gram of green beans. Spiking with FFA generated higher FFT concentrations than with unloaded beans. Adding 3 mg/g FFA resulted in 390 ng/g FFT in the roasted beans compared to 246 ng/g in the unloaded reference.

Figure 1: FFT formed during roasting of coffee beans spiked with FFA and/or cysteine.

The highest FFT level was obtained when beans were spiked with both cysteine (3 mg/g) and FFA (1 mg/g). Because FFA boosts FFT generation during coffee roasting it is suggested as key intermediate to FFT under coffee roasting conditions.

Spiking green coffee with deuterium labelled d_2 -FFA

Next, green coffee was spiked with deuterium labelled d_2 -FFA. The resulting mass spectra of FFT, furfural and furfuryl methyl sulphide (Figure 2) indicate to which extent deuterium labelled and unlabelled isotopologues are formed upon roasting. The mass spectrum of FFT (Figure 2A) was composed of the mass spectra of unlabelled FFT and labelled d_2 -FFT. Analysis of the indicator ions m/z 114 and m/z 116 points to a portion of 41% labelled d_2 -FFT. Indeed d_2 -FFT forms from d_2 -FFA added to the beans. Presumably, FFA from endogenous precursors was also converted to FFT during roasting.

Figure 2B shows the mass spectrum of furfural, which is exclusively unlabelled. Singly labelled d-furfural would be expected if formed from d_2 -FFA. As this was not the case, although furfural was formed during roasting, it did not stem from FFA. Furfuryl methyl sulphide (Figure 2C) was a mixture of d_2 -labelled and unlabelled compound. This points to FFA as precursor, as in the case of FFT.

Figure 2: Mass spectra of compounds formed during roasting coffee beans spiked with d_2 -FFA.

The ratio of labelled to unlabelled FFA and FFT during coffee roasting changed during the roasting process. During the first 2 min unlabelled FFA was not detected (Figure 3, left). Only after 3 min unlabelled FFA from endogenous precursors appears, proportionally increasing until 5 min. Both unlabelled and labelled d_2 -FFT appeared only after 3 min roasting. The portion of unlabelled FFT dominated and increased until the end of roasting. Labelled d_2 -FFT formed from labelled d_2 -FFA, while unlabelled FFT seems to be formed from the unlabelled intermediate FFA and possibly other precursors.

Figure 3: Proportion of d_2 -labelled versus unlabelled FFA and FFT, respectively in roasted coffee (150 to 200 °C, 5 min), spiked with d_2 -FFA (2 mg/g) prior to roasting.

When green coffee was spiked with increasing amounts of d_2 -FFA (0-3 mg/g) the proportion of labelled d_2 -FFT to labelled FFT increased as indicated by the ratios of m/z ions 114 to 116 in Table 1, which shows the relative percentage of ions in the mass spectra of FFT. Detection of m/z 116 is not only due to d_2 -FFT but also to a small extent of undeuterated FFT that carries the natural sulphur isotope ^{34}S (natural abundance 4.2%), the value for m/z 116 needs to be corrected.

The fact that increasing amounts of labelled d_2 -FFA lead to proportionally more labelled FFT in the roasted beans further substantiates the role of FFA as key intermediate to FFT in coffee.

Table 1: Influence of the quantity of spiked d_2 -FFA in coffee beans on the ratio of FFT m/z ions after roasting.

m/z	d_2 -FFA (mg/g)			
	0	1	2	3
114	89%	70%	60%	50%
115	6%	6%	6%	6%
116	5%	21%	31%	39%
117		2%	2%	3%
118		1%	1%	2%

Formation pathway from FFA to FFT during coffee roasting

Our results revealed that FFA was not converted into furfural during coffee roasting. Furthermore, earlier studies showed that furfural is not converted into FFT during roasting neither [5]. Therefore, a formation pathway from FFA to FFT without furfural is suggested.

Kreppenhof and co-workers had suggested a formation pathway to substituted catechol during coffee roasting that involves the formation of furfuryl cation from FFA [9]. The furfuryl cation then binds in an electrophilic attack to catechol, formed from chlorogenic acid during roasting, resulting in 4-furfurylcatechol.

A similar pathway is suggested for the formation of FFT, which also starts with the formation of furfuryl cation from FFA. As illustrated in Figure 4, the furfuryl cation attacks the thiol group of protein-bound cysteine resulting in the intermediate protein-bound S-furfurylcysteine. Subsequent elimination releases FFT and leaves protein-bound dehydroalanine.

The suggested formation pathway is in agreement with our experimental findings and backed by literature that suggests that FFT precursors are water insoluble.

Figure 4: Suggested pathway from FFA to FFT during coffee roasting.

Conclusion

The study showed that coffee beans spiked with FFA increased the FFT level after roasting and thus, substantiating the role of FFA as FFT precursor. Spiking with labelled d_2 -FFA generated labelled d_2 -FFT. On the other hand, only unlabelled furfural was found. These findings further corroborate the central role of FFA in FFT formation confirming it as key intermediate to FFT in roasted coffee. Furfural, in contrast, apparently plays no major role as FFT intermediate. On this basis, a pathway to FFT is suggested that involves the reaction of FFA with protein-bound cysteine.

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